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Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR
SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF FLUCONAZOLE AND
TINIDAZOLE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE
FORMS BY RP-HPLC**T.Venkatesh¹, M.Chaitanya², P.Aravindra Reddy³

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Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

*RP-HPLC method was developed and validated as per ICH guidelines for the estimation of Fluconazole and Tinidazole. Simultaneous Estimation of Fluconazole and Tinidazole were carried out by RP- HPLC using Ortho phosphoric acid buffer & methanol, and column Inertsil C₁₈ (250*4.6 mm, 5µm) as a stationary phase and peak was observed at 213 nm which was selected as a wavelength for quantitative estimation. After the development of the method, it was validated for various parameters. It was found that recovery value of pure drug was between 99 % to 101% which indicates that the method is accurate and also reveals that commonly used excipients and additives present in the pharmaceutical formulations were not interfering in the proposed methods. The ruggedness of the method was checked by different analysts and found that the results were nearly same which indicates that the method is rugged. Based on the results observed, it was concluded that proposed method can be used for routine analysis of fluconazole and tinidazole.*

Key words: *Fluconazole, Tinidazole anti-protozoal agent, linearity, accuracy, precision.*

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INTRODUCTION:

HPLC today is the product of quarter century of refinement, driven by technical advances and economic competition in a USD 2 Billion plus equipment market. Recently, manufactures have improved HPLC'S performance easier.

Tinidazole is a synthetic anti-protozoal agent. Tinidazole demonstrates activity both in vitro and in clinical infections against the following protozoa: *Trichomonas vaginalis*, *Giardia duodenalis* (also termed *G. lamblia*), and *Entamoeba histolytica*. The free nitro radical generated as a result of this reduction is believed to be responsible for the anti-

protozoal activity. It is suggested that the toxic free radicals covalently bind to DNA, causing DNA damage and leading to cell death. The mechanism by which tinidazole exhibits activity against *Giardia* and *Entamoeba* species is not known, though it is probably similar.

Fluconazole is a highly selective inhibitor of fungal cytochrome P450 dependent enzyme lanosterol 14- α -demethylase. This enzyme functions to convert lanosterol to ergosterol. Fluconazole is a synthetic anti-fungal agent (azoles, chemically imidazole derivative).

Figure 1: Structure of fluconazole

Figure 2: Structure of tinidazole

The main objective of the present work is to establish a stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Fluconazole and Tinidazole in combined dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

HPLC with WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 separation module, PDA detector. All chemicals were AR grade.

HPLC method development and validation:**Mobile phase optimization:**

Initially the mobile phase tried was methanol: Ammonium acetate buffer and Methanol: phosphate

buffer with various combinations of pH as well as varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to potassium dihydrogen phosphate with buffer (pH 3.0), Methanol in proportion 30: 70 v/v respectively.

Wave length selection:

UV spectrum of 10 μ g / ml Fluconazole and Tinidazole in diluents (mobile phase composition) was recorded by scanning in the range of 200nm to 400nm. From the UV spectrum wavelength selected as 213. At this wavelength both the drugs show good absorbance.

Optimization of column:

The method was performed with various columns like C₁₈ column, hypersil column, lichrosorb, and inertsil ODS column. Inertsil ODS (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 0.8ml/min flow.

Preparation of phosphate buffer:

Accurately weighed 6.8 grams of KH₂PO₄ was taken in a 1000ml volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted to 1000ml with HPLC water and the volume was adjusted to pH 3.0 with Orthophosphoric acid.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 300 ml (30%) of above buffer and 700 ml of Methanol HPLC (70%) were mixed and degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of the tinidazole & fluconazole standard & sample solution:**Standard solution preparation:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Fluconazole and Tinidazole 10mg of working standard into a 10mL & 100ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette 3ml & 0.3ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Sample Solution Preparation:

Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 10 mg of Fluconazole and Tinidazole (marketed formulation) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette 3 ml of

Tinidazole and Fluconazole of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure: Inject 20 µL of the standard, sample into the chromatographic system and measure the areas for Fluconazole and Tinidazole peaks and calculate the %Assay by using the formula.

System suitability:

Tailing factor for the peaks due to fluconazole and tinidazole in standard solution should not be more than 2.0. Theoretical plates for the fluconazole and tinidazole peaks in standard solution should not be less than 2000.

Accuracy:

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Fluconazole and Tinidazole 10mg of working standard into a 10mL & 100ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Linearity:

Preparation of stock solution: Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 10 mg of Fluconazole and Tinidazole (marketed formulation) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Chromatogram for tinidazole and fluconazole

Column	:	Inertsil C ₁₈ (4.6 x 250mm, 5µm)
Buffer pH	:	3.0.
Mobile phase	:	30% buffer 70% Methanol
Flow rate	:	1.0 ml per min
Wavelength	:	213 nm
Temperature	:	ambient
Run time	:	10 min

Figure 3: chromatogram for blank

From the above chromatogram it was observed that there are no interferences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Figure 4: Chromatogram for tinidazole and fluconazole sample preparation

From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Tinidazole and Fluconazole peaks are well separated.

Retention time of Tinidazole– 2.057min

Retention time of Fluconazole- 3.663min.

Table 1: Results of system suitability parameters for tinidazole and fluconazole

Name	Retention time (min)	Area (μ V sec)	Height (μ V)	USP resolution	USP tailing	USP plate count
Tinidazole	2.5	124505	213642		1.2	4673.4
Fluconazole	3.9	1308495	154566	6 0	1.3	6090.3

Table 2: Accuracy (recovery) data for Tinidazole

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	656659.5	5.0	5.036	100.7%	99.84%
100%	1304258	10.0	10.003	100.0%	
150%	1854608	14.4	14.224	98.780%	

Table 3: Accuracy (recovery) data for Fluconazole

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	65800	5.3	5.34	100.8%	100.51%
100%	124353	10	10.10	100.01%	
150%	177940	14.2	14.45	99.68%	

Linearity:

The linearity range was found to lie from 100 μ g/ml to 500 μ g/ml of Tinidazole, 5 μ g/ml to 25 μ g/ml of Fluconazole and chromatograms are shown below.

Figure 5: chromatogram for linearity concentration-100 μ g/ml of Tinidazole & 5 μ g/ml of Fluconazole

Figure 6: Calibration graph for Tinidazole

Figure 7: Calibration graph for Fluconazole

Table 4: Analytical performance parameters of Tinidazole and Fluconazole

Parameters	Tinidazole	Fluconazole
Slope (m)	66574	12529
Intercept (c)	53592	50245
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.999	0.999

Limit of detection for tinidazole and fluconazole:

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio

Figure 8: chromatogram of Tinidazole & Fluconazole showing LOD

Table 5: Results of LOD

Drug name	Baseline noise (μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Tinidazole	52	152	2.9
Fluconazole	52	156	3

Limit of quantification (LOQ)

The lowest concentration of the sample was prepared with respect to the base line noise and measured the signal to noise ratio.

Figure 9: Chromatogram of Tinidazole & Fluconazole showing LOQ

Table 6: Results of LOQ

Drug name	Baseline noise (μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Tinidazole	52	522	10.03
Fluconazole	52	524	10.1

CONCLUSION:

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tools of the analysis. The estimation of Tinidazole and Fluconazole was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was pH 3.0 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 70:30 % v/ v. Inertsil C₁₈ column C₁₈ (4.6 x 150mm, 5µm) or equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 213 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. the linearity range of Tinidazole and Fluconazole were found to be from 100-500 µg/ml of Tinidazole and 1-5µg/ml of Fluconazole. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999. The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Tinidazole and Fluconazole. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit. The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements. It inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

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